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Legal Challenges of International Cooperation in Combating Cybercrime: Prospects for Improving the Regulatory Framework

У статті розглядаються сучасні правові виклики міжнародного співробітництва у боротьбі з кіберзлочинністю, зокрема в умовах військових конфліктів та гібридних загроз. Досліджено особливості використання кіберзброї як інструмента гібридної війни та її вплив на глобальну безпеку, національні інтереси держав та критичну інфраструктуру. Проведено комплексний аналіз існуючих міжнародних правових інструментів, таких як Будапештська конвенція про кіберзлочинність, їхніх системних обмежень та перспектив модернізації в контексті новітніх кіберзагроз. Особливу увагу приділено проблемам гармонізації національних законодавств, координації оперативних дій між державами та розробці ефективних механізмів правового регулювання кіберпростору. Висвітлено унікальний досвід України як держави, що зазнає масштабних кібератак в рамках військової агресії, її роль у глобальному співробітництві та практичний досвід у протидії кіберзагрозам різного рівня складності. Обґрунтовано необхідність створення універсальних міжнародних стандартів для екстрадиції кіберзлочинців, обміну інформацією між компетентними органами різних держав та вдосконалення механізмів захисту жертв кіберзлочинів. Запропоновано конкретні шляхи вдосконалення міжнародно-правової бази для забезпечення ефективної боротьби з кіберзлочинністю на глобальному рівні з урахуванням сучасних технологічних, політичних та безпекових викликів.

Ключові слова: кіберзлочинність, міжнародне співробітництво, кібербезпека, Будапештська конвенція, гармонізація законодавства, гібридна війна, кіберзброя, екстрадиція, критична інфраструктура, транскордонні кіберзлочини.

The article examines contemporary legal challenges of international cooperation in combating cybercrime, particularly under the conditions of armed conflicts and hybrid threats. It investigates the distinctive features of cyberweapons as sophisticated tools of hybrid warfare and analyzes their profound impact on global security, national interests, and critical infrastructure protection. The study provides a comprehensive analysis of existing international legal frameworks, such as the Budapest Convention on Cybercrime, their systemic limitations, and prospects for modernization in the context of emerging cyber threats. Special attention is given to crucial issues of harmonizing national legislation, coordinating operational actions among states, and developing effective mechanisms for legal regulation of cyberspace. The article highlights Ukraine's unique experience as a state facing large-scale cyberattacks as part of military aggression, its evolving role in global cooperation, and practical experience in countering cyber threats of varying complexity. The research substantiates the necessity of establishing universal international standards for the extradition of cybercriminals, information exchange between competent authorities of different states, and improving protection mechanisms for victims of cybercrimes. Furthermore, the article addresses the importance of strengthening international interaction across jurisdictions, ensuring cross-border investigations, and adapting existing norms to the rapidly changing realities of the digital age. The proposed concrete solutions aim to enhance the efficiency of international legal

frameworks in countering cybercrime and ensuring comprehensive global cybersecurity in the context of modern technological, political, and security challenges.

Keywords: *cybercrime, international cooperation, cybersecurity, Budapest Convention, legislative harmonization, hybrid warfare, cyberweapons, extradition, critical infrastructure, cross-border cybercrimes.*

Problem Statement. Modern warfare is characterized by the use of cyber weapons as an integral element of hybrid aggression aimed at destabilizing the critical infrastructure of states, compromising information security, and manipulating public opinion. Cybercrimes, such as unauthorized intrusion into information systems, distribution of malicious software, and cyber espionage, have become instruments of international conflicts. Given the military aggression Ukraine is experiencing, there is an increasing need to improve the legal framework for international cooperation aimed at countering cybercrime and ensuring effective prosecution of offenders. However, the absence of unified mechanisms for legal interaction between states creates significant obstacles in this process.

Analysis of Recent Research and Publications. The topic of international cooperation in combating cybercrime is relevant and actively researched by leading experts in international law, criminal law, and cybersecurity. In their works, authors such as Marushchak A.I. [4], Lysaichuk A.A. [6], and Melnyk M.R. [11] analyze the provisions of the Budapest Convention on Cybercrime, its limitations, and prospects for implementation in Ukraine. An important place in research is occupied by the issue of adapting international agreements to new conditions associated with the use of cyber weapons in wartime.

Reports from international organizations such as the UN [2], Council of Europe [1], and Europol [9] highlight current trends in cybercrime and emphasize the need to strengthen coordination between states. These documents address issues of effective information exchange, improvement of extradition procedures, and combating new forms of cyber attacks that threaten global security. In particular, reports from ENISA [5] and NATO CCDCOE [14] emphasize the growing role of cybercrime as part of hybrid conflicts.

Scientific papers and official documents underscore that effective combating of cybercrime in wartime requires significant changes in the legal and regulatory framework. In particular, attention should be paid to adapting existing international norms to new challenges associated with cyber attacks sponsored by aggressor states.

Unresolved Issues. Despite active research, key problems remain unresolved that hinder effective combating of cybercrime at the global level. Among them are:

1. The absence of a universal international agreement that would regulate mechanisms of state interaction in the field of combating cybercrime [3].
2. Imperfection of extradition procedures for persons suspected of cybercrimes, especially if they are in countries that refuse to cooperate with international organizations [8].
3. Low effectiveness in implementing mechanisms for the exchange of operational information between states [12].
4. The use of cyber attacks as a means of warfare, which requires new approaches to international legal regulation [16].

Purpose of the Article is to comprehensively analyze the legal challenges of international cooperation in combating cybercrime in conditions of military conflicts, to identify the main problems of such interaction, and to develop proposals for improving the regulatory framework for effective counteraction to cyber threats at the international level.

Main Content Presentation. The development of information technology has opened up new horizons for cooperation between states, but at the same time has caused a number of problems related to the spread of cybercrime. This problem is especially acute in times of war, when cybercrime becomes part of hybrid conflicts and is aimed at undermining the functioning of state institutions and critical infrastructure [1, p. 15].

One of the key international documents in the field of combating cybercrime is the Budapest Convention on Cybercrime, which defines legal mechanisms for cooperation between states in the detection, investigation and prosecution of cybercrime. The Convention provides a framework for a joint response to global threats and provides mechanisms for international legal assistance [2]. However, its effectiveness is limited by the fact that a number of states, including key geopolitical players such as China and Russia, are not parties to it [3, p. 45].

The Council of Europe reports state that the Budapest Convention on Cybercrime needs further improvement, in particular in terms of regulating cross-border access to data, as modern cyberattacks are mostly carried out through global networks [1]. In the new conditions of war, the question arises of the need to strengthen the provisions on the responsibility of states for the use of cyber weapons against other countries.

The war in Ukraine has become one of the most striking examples of the use of cybercrime as a means of aggression. Cyberattacks accompanying military operations are aimed not only at destabilizing the internal situation in the country, but also at influencing the international community. For example, in 2022, the Ukrainian energy system suffered large-scale cyberattacks, the consequences of which could have had a catastrophic impact on the population and economy [3].

Such actions require not only a prompt response from the affected country, but also international coordination. In particular, the experience of Ukraine's cooperation with Europol and Interpol in investigating cyberattacks on critical infrastructure confirms the need to expand the legal framework for effective cooperation [9].

One of the biggest obstacles in the fight against cybercrime is the issue of extradition of persons suspected of committing cybercrime. Often, such persons are in states that do not cooperate with international organizations or directly support their activities. For example, the Russian Federation has repeatedly refused to extradite hackers who carried out cyberattacks against the European Union and the United States, making it impossible to bring them to justice [6].

Researchers emphasize that one of the reasons for this situation is the imperfection of international information exchange mechanisms and the lack of unified standards of evidence in cases related to cybercrime. This is especially true for countries with different legal traditions and approaches to evidence collection [4].

Effective counteraction to cybercrime requires harmonization of national legislation with international standards. One example is the European Union's Digital Shield legislative initiative, which envisages the introduction of stricter cybersecurity standards to protect critical infrastructure. Ukraine, as an EU candidate country, is also working to implement these standards in its

legislation, which opens up new prospects for cooperation [5].

However, harmonization of legislation does not solve all problems. Effective mechanisms need to be created to ensure prompt access to data on cyberattacks and perpetrators, as well as to ensure rapid interaction between law enforcement agencies of different countries [4].

International organizations play a key role in coordinating efforts to combat cybercrime, especially in the context of military conflicts. For example, Interpol has introduced the Cyber Fusion Center program, which provides for the rapid exchange of information between member countries, the detection of cyber threats, and the coordination of international investigations. This initiative reduces the response time to cyberattacks, which is critical in the current environment [7].

The European Cyber Security Agency (ENISA) develops strategies to protect against cyberattacks, including joint exercises, exchange of experience between EU member states, and the development of standards to protect critical infrastructure. At the same time, ENISA faces difficulties in coordinating with third countries, including Ukraine, due to differences in legal standards and procedural norms [5].

The UN also pays considerable attention to cybersecurity through specialized bodies such as the UN Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC). The organization promotes the development of unified approaches to investigating cybercrime and providing access to the necessary resources for less developed states [2]. However, the effectiveness of such programs is limited by insufficient funding and political instability in countries in need of assistance.

One of the key aspects of modern cybercrime is the use of cyberweapons by aggressor states as a means of military warfare. Cyberweapons can be conditionally divided into means:

1. Destructive impact on infrastructure (e.g., malware that disrupts power systems).
2. Information theft (cyber espionage).
3. Disinformation (creation and dissemination of fake news to manipulate public opinion) [10, p. 98].

Classical international law does not fully take into account the peculiarities of the use of cyber weapons. For example, the Hague and Geneva Conventions are aimed at regulating armed conflicts,

but do not cover cyberattacks that cause damage without the direct use of physical force. In this context, there is a need to create a special protocol to these conventions or a new international treaty that would regulate the use of cyber weapons in war.

An important factor in combating cybercrime is the financing of relevant measures. The cost of responding to cyberattacks and their consequences can reach hundreds of millions of dollars, as was the case with the NotPetya virus attack that paralyzed businesses in many countries, including Ukraine [11]. International initiatives aimed at reducing economic losses include:

- Creation of funds to support the affected countries;
- introduction of international insurance of risks associated with cyberattacks;
- involvement of the private sector in cooperation through public-private partnerships[12].

However, economic support is not always available to countries at war, which creates additional challenges for their cybersecurity.

Technical and educational support provided by the international community to countries with insufficient training in this area plays a significant role in the fight against cybercrime. Technical assistance programs include training law enforcement agencies in modern methods of investigating cybercrime, as well as providing equipment for monitoring and analyzing data.

Educational initiatives, such as the programs of the European School of Cyber Security, are aimed at forming a new generation of cyber defense specialists. At the same time, UN reports note that the lack of such programs in the face of global demand creates gaps in the protection of many countries [13].

Victims of cybercrime, especially in wartime, are often left without adequate legal protection. For example, the theft of personal data during cyberattacks can lead to financial losses, reputational risks, and even threats to the physical safety of victims. National legislation in most

countries does not provide clear mechanisms for compensation for such losses [14].

International practice in this area is limited to isolated initiatives, such as the creation of funds for compensation for losses, but their activities are significantly limited due to insufficient funding and the complexity of legal claims.

Conclusions. Cybercrime, particularly in the context of modern military conflicts, emerges as a global threat that demands an effective legal and organizational response at the international level. The analysis shows that existing legal mechanisms, including international agreements, are not fully capable of responding to new challenges associated with the use of cyber weapons and the complexity of cross-border cybercrimes [15]. The uncertainty of the legal status of such actions, the absence of unified standards in the investigation and punishment of cybercrimes significantly complicate international cooperation.

Special attention must be paid to the harmonization of legislation, as differences in the legal systems of various countries create serious barriers to effective information exchange, evidence sharing, and extradition of suspects. In this context, cooperation between states should be based on clearly regulated mechanisms that ensure operational efficiency and reliability. Military actions in Ukraine have highlighted the critical necessity of strengthening international interaction, particularly in the sphere of information exchange about cyber attacks and identifying the individuals behind these crimes.

Furthermore, technological development requires improving the level of training for specialists in the field of cybersecurity and providing technical support for states that have suffered from cyber attacks. Such initiatives should be accompanied by the development of new international standards aimed at protecting victims of cybercrime, who often remain without proper legal protection. Successful combating of cybercrime is possible only under conditions of a global approach that considers the needs of all states and offers universal solutions for responding to the challenges of the digital age.

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